

PROVERBS AND SAYINGS AS REFLECTION OF PEOPLE' PERCEPTION IN THEIR LIFE

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Annotation: In this article you will be explained the necessity of proverbs. It is devoted to the significance of proverbs and sayings in people's everyday life or communication. We know that proverbs are wise sayings that can give advice about real life. They are culturally specific, yet their meaning has the universality and everyone can relate to them in some way and on some level. There is a proverb for almost in any situation. There are some English proverbs and sayings and their equivalents with Uzbek language.

Keywords: specific features, culture's perception, own identity signs, comparison of proverbs, social history, unrelated languages, phraseology.

Proverbs and sayings represent a national cultural heritage and are a favoured material for learning in a foreign language classroom. There are some specific features, characterizing the colour of some original and national culture with its centuries in the past. Proverbs and sayings contain deep sense and national wisdom, which have roots far in an old history. They reflect people's way of thoughts in life. Moreover, proverbs sometimes do not give any meaning when they are translated word by word. In addition, proverbs give students primary information about grammar, syntax and phraseology, and information about the culture of the target language country.

There are lots of short statements containing advice for the people in general that reflect collective wisdom of our forefathers and have been passed down to successive generations. People make use of these sayings and proverbs in daily lives and use the terms interchangeably. While there are many similarities between a saying and a proverb, there are also differences that will be talked about in this article. Let's see some differences between sayings and proverbs.

Sayings are familiar expressions those are often repeated. Also referred to as an adage, a saying is something that was said in the past and has become popular to be often repeated in daily life of common people. If you look up a dictionary, you would

find that the synonyms given for a saying are aphorism, proverb, maxim, adage and so on.

Something that is said is a saying. Sayings are considered clever expressions that hold their value and significance even today though they were said and used in ancient times. It is hard to trace the origins of sayings as they have been there since time immemorial, handed down to successive generations. Sayings are short and direct. Most of them make use of simple language to make them easily understandable. Different types of sayings, they are proverbs those are the most popular. Take a look at the following sentences that are sayings to understand their hidden value and wisdom.

- A stitch in time saves nine
- Where there is smoke, there is fire
- Honesty is the best policy

Proverb are type of sayings those contains a piece of advice or simply contains truth or any other universal value. They are short statements those are popular and people make use of a proverb to express their feelings. A proverb can say a lot more than a thousand words. Morality, truth, wisdom, friendship, loyalty, etc. are the values that are glorified with the use of these proverbs. These proverbs are based upon common sense and lay down the foundation of code of conduct as they are as much true or useful today as they were hundreds of years ago. Take a look at the following proverbs.

- Money does not grow on trees
- The early bird catches the worms
- Pen is mightier than sword

What is the difference between Saying and Proverb?

- A saying is something that has been said, and there are many different types of sayings such as adage, maxim, aphorisms, proverbs, etc.
- Out of all the sayings, it is the proverbs that are believed to be the most popular around the world.
- Sayings are pithy statements that express a universal value.
- Proverb is mostly common sense wisdom while saying can be broader to contain maxim and adage too.

- So, all proverbs are basically sayings, but not all sayings are proverbs.

In this article the most attention is paid to the translation of Uzbek proverbs and sayings into the English language, mainly the proverbs and sayings from the great

dictionary “Devoni lug'at ut- turk” by Mahmud al-Kashgari and another internet resources have been analysed. Here are given some examples:

1. Uzbek form: “Qush qanoti bilan, er oti bilan”. English form: “The bird (reaches its goal) by wing (and similarly) the man (reaches his goal) by horse”.

2. Uzbek form: “O’z uying o’lan to’shaging”. English form: “ East or West, home is best”. Meaning: There is no best place like home or your own home is the most comfortable place to be.

3. “Jo’jani kuzda sanaymiz”, “ Don’t count your chicken before they hatch”. Meaning: Don’t think you can do everything you want without any help.

4. Uzbek form: “Yalqovga eshik ostonasi ham tog' tepasidek ko'rinadi". English form: “For the lazy man a threshold becomes a mountain pass”.

5. Uzbek form: “O't degan bilan og'iz kuymas". English form: “If one says “Fire” his mouth doesn't catch fire". This is coined about someone who apologizes for something he said.

6. Uzbek form: “Zamon o'tar, kishi to'yimas, inson bolasi mangu qolmas". English form: “Time (zamon) passes and man does not perceive it, the sons of Adam do not live forever”.

7. Uzbek form: “Hechdan ko’ra kech”, “Better late than never”. Meaning: It is always better to arrive or do something late than not at all.

8. Uzbek form: "Tulki o'z uyasiga qarab irillasa (ulasa, hursa) qo'tir bo'ladi". English form: “When a fox yelps at its own den he becomes mangy". This is coined about someone who blames his own tribe or clan or city, to rebuke him and his fault-finding.

9. Uzbek form: "Yegan og'iz uyalar". English form: “When the mouth eats the eye is ashamed". This is coined about someone who has “eaten” another person's gift and then is ashamed for failing to do what he should in return.

10. “Maqtanma g’oz hunaring oz’, “People who live in a glass houses should not throw stones”. Meaning: you shouldn’t criticize other people if you are not perfect yourself.

11. Uzbek form: “Ko’r ko’rni qorong’uda topadi”, English form: “Birds of a feather flock together” Meaning: People like to spend time with others who are similar to them.

12. “Ishlamagan tishlamaydi”, “There’s no such thing as a free lunch”, Meaning: Things that are offered for free always have a hidden cost.

13. “Never look a gift horse in the mouth”, Meaning: If someone offers you a gift, don’t question it.

Having written about this theme I realized that, the role of proverbs and sayings in our life can hardly be overestimated. Nowadays there are a lot of ways to keep and transfer information: with the help of audio, visual carriers, and also in electronic version. But a lot of years ago, when writing even wasn’t developed, But a lot of years ago, when writing even wasn’t developed, the only way to gain the experience was our language. Even now we have our ancestors’ messages in the form of songs, fairy-tales, and ceremonies. But the most brief, informative and perhaps the most frequently used messages are proverbs and sayings.

Proverbs and sayings are an integral part of the process of mastering a foreign language. Language training should take place in the conditions of the real using of the language or should imitate these conditions as precisely as possible. Proverbs and sayings have been using in the educational process for a long time. They help to express the same thought by different words; they are irreplaceable in the mastering dialogical and monological speech, making it alive, colorful and acute.

Also there are a lot of proverbs which are common for the most people in the world. Because proverbs are usually spoken and not written, they relate to everyday wisdom people want to convey in speech. As a result, they relate matters or everyday interest, such as the weather: March comes in like a lion and goes out like a lamb, folk medicine or observations about health: An apple a day keeps the doctor away and Early to bed, early to rise, religion: Man proposes, God disposes, family: Spare the rod and spoil the child, the law: A man's house is his castle, and superstitions: Marry in March, repent always.

Proverbs are usually illustrated with homely imagery using household objects, farm animals, pets, and events of daily life. Many proverbs are based on customs that are obsolete. For example, in English, the proverb If the cap fits, wear it refers to the medieval fool’s cap used in parts of Europe. Quite frequently, a proverb’s origin is unknown. The same proverb can be found in the same language in several forms. For example, in English, the proverb “Money is the root of all evil” is also used as “The love of money is the root of all evil”.

As it is said in Encyclopedia Britannica that comparison of proverbs found in various parts of the world have shown that basic human behaviors and observations about various aspects of life are similar across languages, cultures and continents. For

example, the biblical saying "An eye for an eye, a tooth for a tooth" has an equivalent among the Nandi speakers East Africa: "A goat's hide buys a goat's hide, and a gourd, a gourd". And also its equivalent form in the Uzbek language as follows: "Qonga qon, jonga jon". Often, the same proverb can be found in many variants in languages and cultures related by linguistic or social history, and even in unrelated languages. In Europe countries, a large number of proverbs have variants in most major languages. For example, the proverb known in English as "A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush" originated in Medieval Latin, and variants of it are found in Romanian, Italian.

To sum up, It's mentioned above opinions we can say that we have two types of proverbs: those with a common, universal morality, guide for the practice of virtue, similar in all countries, if not in the form, at least in the message; and those which are particular, born from a historical fact, a local custom or a specific event. They have their own identity signs which characterize the place or time of origin.

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